

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a Carbonate Reservoir

R2.3 Lithofacial layer model

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CONTENT

1 INTRODUCTION.....	3
2 WELL LOGS FOR LITHOFACIES	3
2.1 Input data preparation and formatting.....	3
2.2 Well logs	4
3 STRATIGRAPHIC AND TECTONIC EVOLUTION.....	29
3.1 Chrono- and lithostratigraphic units	29
3.2 Paleogeographical evolution	30
3.3 Extensional and compressional regimes of the tectonic evolution of the Zar-3 area ...	36
4 REGIONAL 2D SECTIONS IN ZAR-3 AREA	37
5 MICROSCOPIC EVALUATION OF LITHOFACIAL TYPES OF RESERVOIR AND SEAL ROCKS	41
5.1 Microscopy in translucent, reflected and fluorescent light	43
6 OPTICAL POROSITY OF RESERVOIR AND SEAL ROCKS.....	50
7 LITHOFACIAL 3D MODEL.....	52
8 CONCLUSIONS.....	55
REFERENCES.....	56

1 INTRODUCTION

Lithofacial model provides information on the distribution of depositional environments and resulting lithologies for the main stratigraphic units, which build the Zar-3 oil & gas field and future CO₂ storage complex. It is based on well logs, mud logs tied with seismic data as well as on the core sample analyses. Lithofacial model deals with the reservoir horizon and underlying and overlying strata. The purpose is to improve the input data for the reservoir dynamic modelling and simulations in WPs 3 and 8.

Good knowledge of lithofacies patterns makes it possible to interpolate and extrapolate rock types and reservoir or sealing properties to the undrilled parts of the storage site. The work in task 2.3 was performed jointly by MND with support of CGS.

2 WELL LOGS FOR LITHOFACIES

2.1 Input data preparation and formatting

Well data are described in detail in the R2.2 3D geometric model report. The well heads positions and trajectories are shown in Figs. 2-1 and 2-2. 75 core samples were collected from the MND a.s. repository for detailed facial analysis.

Fig. 2-1: Location of the well heads in the Zar-3 area of interest.

Fig. 2-2: 3D view of exploration and production wells in the Zar-3 oil and gas field with stratigraphy and position of core samples. Jurassic Vranovice Fm. shown in light blue (cyan) is the principal reservoir.

2.2 Well logs

The area (Fig. 2-1) comprises a total of 22 deep wells; 14 wells penetrated the reservoir itself and 4 are side-tracks. Most of the wells are deviated or horizontal. Overview of the investigated wells are listed in Tab. 2-1. The well logs include depth intervals, stratigraphy, lithostratigraphy, schematic lithology, cored intervals, available samples, perforated intervals and well tests results. Processed data were kindly provided by MND, a.s. and Geofond archive of the Czech Geological Survey. Data were processed using the Strater 5 and Surfer 13 of Golden Software LLC.

Tab. 2-1: Overview of the exploration and production wells in the Zar-3 area.

Well name (UWI)	ID GDO* (no.)	X (S42A)	Y (S42A)	Z (**BSLaA)	Measured depth (m)	Locality (name)	Drilling in (year)
UH3	461118	3644935.55	5437288.21	287.10	2595	Žarošice	1977
UH5	462224	3646632.10	5437377.55	257.85	2050	Archlebov	1978
UH6	461157	3646023.94	5438986.92	366.07	1420	Archlebov	1978
UH9	461159	3642601.79	5436106.40	219.75	2800	Uhřice	1985
UH10	461160	3643385.05	5435389.36	200.43	2911	Uhřice	1982
UH11	461161	3643880.47	5438113.37	226.66	1711	Žarošice	1980
UH12	461162	3645667.50	5439382.03	385.91	1500	Archlebov	1979
UH16	461156	3643072.54	5436774.24	274.88	2800	Uhřice	1986
ZA1	461214	3643548.20	5437234.93	220.76	2867	Žarošice	1965
ZA3	645193	3644202.09	5437240.90	219.28	1923	Žarošice	2001
ZA4	643952	3644197.83	5437256.52	219.25	1901	Žarošice	2002
ZA4A	643954	3644197.83	5437256.52	219.25	1995	Žarošice	2002
ZA5H	655774	3644044.68	5437843.83	247.80	2860	Žarošice	2003
ZA6	655775	3644047.76	5437830.11	247.84	2020	Žarošice	2003
ZA6A	655776	3644047.76	5437830.11	247.84	2032	Žarošice	2003
ZA7	661637	3644204.31	5437233.33	219.26	2120	Žarošice	2003
ZA8AH	731461	3644017.55	5437816.46	248.11	2440	Žarošice	2014
ZA8H	730845	3644017.55	5437816.46	248.11	2347	Žarošice	2014
ZA9AH	663046	3644206.44	5437225.53	218.64	2475	Žarošice	2004
ZA9H	663047	3644206.44	5437225.53	218.64	1920	Žarošice	2004
ZA12	-	3644028.16	5437818.91	247.47	2030	Žarošice	2017
ZA14H	687067	3644207.92	5437219.66	219.27	2255	Žarošice	2008

* ID GDO = ID of geologically documented object in on-line map application of Borehole surveys

** Z coordinates are given in meters above the Baltic Sea level after adjustment.

Lithological and stratigraphic profiles with well logs use legends shown in Fig. 2-3. Well logs are ordered alphabetically according to the well name in this chapter (Figs. 2-4 to 2-25). All available data were compiled and quality-checked, and put into a user-friendly format in graphic form. The well-log records were provided by MND in digital LAS format.

Fig. 2-3: Legends to the well logs in the Zar-3 field.

The lithofacies distribution is legible from the lithological column in the well profiles (Figs. 2-4 to 2-25), more details are provided in the following chapters 3 and 5.

Fig. 2-4: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH3.

Fig. 2-5: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH5.

Fig. 2-6: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH6.

Fig. 2-7: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH9.

Fig. 2-8: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH10.

Fig. 2-9: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH11.

Fig. 2-10: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH12.

Fig. 2-11: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the UH16.

Fig. 2-12: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA1.

Fig. 2-13: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA3.

Fig. 2-14: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA4.

Fig. 2-15: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA4A.

Fig. 2-16: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA5H.

Fig. 2-17: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA6.

Fig. 2-18: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA6A.

Fig. 2-19: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA7.

Fig. 2-20: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA8H.

Fig. 2-21: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA8AH well.

Fig. 2-22: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA9H well.

Fig. 2-23: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA9AH well.

Fig. 2-25: Stratigraphy, lithology, cores, perforations and well logs in the ZA14H well.

3 STRATIGRAPHIC AND TECTONIC EVOLUTION

Lithological and stratigraphic evolution of the SE Bohemian Massif has been studied by Ladwein (1988), Eliáš and Wessely (1990), Řehánek (1992), Krejčí et al. (1996), Adámek (2005), Pícha et al. (2006) and recently by Opletal (2020).

3.1 Chrono- and lithostratigraphic units

The chronostratigraphic and lithostratigraphic units encountered in Zar-3 oil & gas field are shown in Figs. 3-1 and 3-2.

Fig. 3-1: Stratigraphy and hydrocarbon habitat of the SE margin of Bohemian Massif below Carpathian Foredeep and the allochthonous West Carpathian Flysch Belt (Pícha et al. 2006).

Fig. 3-2: Lithofacies and lithostratigraphy of the Jurassic of the SE margin of the Bohemian Massif (modified from Ladwein 1988, Eliáš and Wessely 1990, Řehánek 1992, Adámek 2005 and Opletal 2020).

3.2 Paleogeographical evolution

A series of paleogeographic maps was prepared based on broader regional geological knowledge, well and seismic data. Starting from the Middle Devonian up to Middle Paleogene they show the areal extent of the lithostratigraphic units (Figs. 3-3 to 3-11) in the area of interest. Many of them represent an erosional relict. In the following paragraphs depositional environment is described. The lithofacies distribution model is described in the individual maps shown in Figs. 3-4 to 3-11.

Fig. 3-3: Major oil and gas reservoirs in the broader Zar-3 area of interest: UGS – underground gas storage (e.g. Dambořice).

Fig. 3-4: Stack of Paleozoic units and crystalline: Upper Carboniferous foreland basin, L. Carboniferous syn-tectonic foreland basin (Culm), U. Devonian (D2-C1) carbonates and M. Devonian continental siliciclastics.

Fig. 3-9: U. Jurassic (Malm) Kurdějov and Ernsbrun Fms. limestones and marls deposited in Seaward shoral environment of the litoral to shallow shelf.

Fig. 3-10: Autochthonous M. Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. (Žarošice Mb.) built by siltstones, sandstones, shales and marls was deposited in the incised valleys in the Jurassic and older units.

3.3 Extensional and compressional regimes of the tectonic evolution of the Zar-3 area

The lithospheric plates drifting during the geological history resulted in different tectonic settings in the following way:

- Middle (M.) – Upper (U.) Devonian – extensional regime, passive continental margin.
- Lower (L.) Carboniferous (Visean) – compressional regime, syn-orogenic foreland basin: Convergence of the Armorican + Avalonian and Brunovistulian plates.
- Triassic to L. Jurassic – extensional regime, opening of Tethys Ocean, passive margin setting, extensive erosion of the Paleozoic.
- M. Jurassic to L. Cretaceous – extensional regime, subsidence and passive margins setting, deposition of fluvial and carbonate bank to upper slope sediments.
- L. Paleogene – subsidence due to approaching Alpine & Carpathian plates, erosion of submarine canyons (Nesvačilka and Žarošice valleys).
- M. Paleogene – deposition of deep-water sediments in the canyons: slumps on steep canyon slopes, general compressional regime, distant foreland basin.
- L. - M. Miocene – compressional and transgressional regimes, deposition sands and shales of marginal foreland basin of the Carpathian Foredeep, Carpathian and Alpine overthrusting – emplacement of the Ždánice and Pouzdřany units of the Carpathian Flysch Belt.

Unconformities:

- Major unconformities occur on top of Paleozoic units due to heavy erosion during the Permian and Triassic.
- Important unconformity evidence erosional events in the Cretaceous and L. Paleogene, which resulted in partial removal of the Jurassic in the submarine canyons.
- Little or no unconformity is observed between the Vranovice and Mikulov Fms. (Oxfordian – Tithonian). Mikulov Fm. onlaps the Vranovice Fm.
- Top of the Nesvačilka Fm. was partly eroded tectonically by the Carpathian thrusting. Unconformity is observed at the thrust plane above the Nesvačilka Fm. and at the base of the allochthonous Ždánice and Pouzdřany units.

4 REGIONAL 2D SECTIONS IN ZAR-3 AREA

Based on well log and stratigraphic correlation, three 2D profiles across the wells were created (Figs. 4-2, 4-3 and 4-4). The profiles are shown in Fig. 4-1.

Fig. 4-1: Location of the three 2D profiles across the wells in the Zar-3 area of interest.

Fig. 4-2: NNW-SSE regional section through the projected UH11, ZA6A, ZA6, ZA3, ZA4A and ZA7 wells.

Fig. 4-3: W-E regional section through the ZA1, ZA3 and UH3 wells.

Fig. 4-4: SW-NE regional section through the UH9, UH16, ZA1 and UH11 wells.

5 MICROSCOPIC EVALUATION OF LITHOFACIAL TYPES OF RESERVOIR AND SEAL ROCKS

Distribution of typical carbonate depositional environments and microfacies is shown in figs. 5-1 (Nosrati et al. 2019) and 5-2 (Bebout and Loucks 1974; Inden & Moore 1983). They both show patch reefs with some similarities to the Zar-3 oil and gas field.

Fig. 5-1: Depositional environment and microfacies distribution in a textbook carbonate type basin (Nosrati et al. 2019).

Fig. 5-2: Depositional model for the K1 shelf margin along the Texas ancestral Gulf of Mexico with patch reefs forming buildups (Bebout & Loucks 1974; Inden & Moore 1983).

Fig. 5-3: Carbonate buildup with dolomitic caprock holding the reef together (Ischia island, Italy). Lower part of the buildup is partly eroded by the sea wave energy.

The Zar-3 carbonate oil and gas field is located in the reservoir built by the Vranovice Fm. It was most probably formed as a patch reef similar to that shown in Fig. 5-2 (Inden & Moore 1983). By the time of the buildup growth, it was larger. Little or no erosion took place prior to deposition of the Mikulov Fm., which onlaps on the Vranovice Fm. In Paleocene, the volume of the reef body was reduced by submarine erosion from the West and North in the Žarošice valley. The final shape of the reservoir was formed in the Eocene, when the silts, clays and sands were deposited in the Nesvačilka and Žarošice submarine valleys (Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb.).

5.1 Microscopy in translucent, reflected and fluorescent light

Detailed microscopic examination of 62 thin sections under plane-polarized (PPL), crossed polarized (XPL), reflected (RL) and fluorescent light (FL) was performed. Two atlases were prepared and stored in the project repository with photomicrographs and petrographic descriptions and interpretations of the depositional environment.

Examples of petrographic types of carbonate rocks from the Zar-3 field are shown below. The emphasis is put on the petrographic evidence of the depositional environments and their changes through the geological time. In many cases, the diagenesis is documented with features like dolomitization, porosity reduction and/or generation of new pore space at the expense of the dissolved mineral grains. The fluid – rock interaction is dealt with in a separate chapter. In the following, the reservoirs are shown first and caprocks.

Reservoir

Fig. 5-4: ZA4A, 1759 (left) and 1778 m (right), Vranovice Fm., brecciated dolostone.

The carbonate strata shown in thin section scan suggest aggradation growth of a patch reef in the Upper Jurassic marginal sea. The darker zones are built by fine grained micrite with organic matter and some impurities, while the white or pale zones consist of coarser grained sparite. This type of stratification is typical in patch or pinnacle reefs. The reefs are usually less than 30 m tall at time of living organisms, but they may reach a much higher thickness in the geological history when combined with subsidence, karstification, brecciation, and sediment redeposition as observed in case of Zar-3 oil and gas field reservoir.

PPL Plane Polarized Light

XPL Crossed Polarizers Light

Fig. 5-5: ZA5H 2094 m, reservoir, Vranovice Fm., oolitic limestone – packstone to grainstone.

Depositional environment - seaward shoral, higher energy, partly recrystallized and leached matrix.

Vuggy and moldic porosity, fissures filled with younger calcite.

Reservoir

Fig. 5-6: ZA3 1 786.4 m, reservoir, Vranovice Fm., brecciated dolostone, planar subhedral crystals of dolomite. Channel and vuggy porosity.

Fig. 5-7: ZA7 1942.4 m, Vranovice Fm., Dolostone nonequigranular. Two types of dolomite crystals: planar euhedral and planar subhedral. Vuggy porosity.

Fig. 5-8: ZA7_1940, TVDSS 1 637.71 m, Vranovice Fm. Dolostone with very fine unimodal planar-s (subheral) to planar-e (euhedral) crystals of dolomite with sucrosic texture.

Dolomitized micritic limestone (mudstone to wackestone), some dolomicrite is preserved and is partly leached forming vugs. A few grains of glauconite. In fluorescence, crystals of dolomite are zonal with several bright and dark green zones, micrite is bright green. Texture of dolomite indicating early phase of dolomitization.

Porosity: vuggy

- A) fine euhedral to subhedral grains of dolomite, clay (dark matter in the bottom of thin sec., PPL)
- B) some bigger crystals of dolomite on the left part (bright), pore (arrow), red rectangle is area zoomed in fig. E and F, plain light (PPL)
- C) leached pores – vugs (p), PPL
- D) fig. C in fluorescence, crystals of dolomite are zoned with bright centers and dark edges, space between grains is partly filled with clay (bright colour)
- E) zoomed area from fig B., mostly euhedral to subhedral crystals of dolomite, pore (p), plain light
- F) fig. E in fluorescence, zoned crystals of dolomite with several bright and dark zone

XRD: Clay + Q + F: 0.6 % Calcite: 0.0 % Dolomite: 20.4 % Dolomite Ca-Fe: 79 %

Fig. 5-9: ZA7 – MD 1 940 m, TVDSS 1 638.75 m, reservoir, Vranovice Fm.

Dolostone with polymodal crystals of dolomite (Fig 5-9) with fine planar-s crystals (subhedral, dark), coarser planar-s to planar-e (euhedral, bright) and planar-c (cement) dolomite. There are some dark seams with small euhedral crystals of dolomite. In fluorescence, crystals of dolomite are zonal with several bright and dark green zones, space between crystals is filled with bright green calcite, in some spaces with orange bituminous matter.

Porosity: vuggy, channel

- A) B) C) fine euhedral to subhedral grains of dolomite, stylolites with clay (dark seams), some bigger crystals of dolomite along stylolites, red rectangle in fig B is zoomed area in fig. E and F, plain light
- D) fig. C in fluorescence, space between grains and stylolites are filled with clay (bright colour)
- E) zoomed area from fig B., mostly euhedral to subhedral crystals of dolomite, plain light
- F) fig. E in fluorescence, zoned crystals of dolomite with several bright and dark zones

XRD - see previous sample ZA7_1940, TVDSS 1637.71 and 1640.3

Caprocks

Fig. 5-10: ZA4 MD 1862 m, TVDSS 1573.29 m, caprock, Nesvačilka Fm./Žarošice mb.

Sandy siltstone (Sisa) composed mainly of subangular to subrounded quartz grains, less feldspar grains, and some charred coaly organic detritus. Space between grains is almost completely filled by clay and partly with dolomite cement. In fluorescence quartz is dark green, cement is bright green, charred organic detritus is black and there is a lot of probably bituminous matter with orange color.

Porosity: interparticle, fracture

- A) quartz grains are white, coaly organic particles are black, feldspars and clay are grey, plain light
- B) coaly organic particle (dark particle in left), plain light
- C) quartz grains are white, coaly organic particles are black, feldspars and clay are grey, plain light
- D) fig. C in fluorescence, quartz and feldspar are darker, clay and carbonate cement are brighter
- E) feldspar (f), quartz (q), coaly organic particle (cp), plain light
- F) fig. E in fluorescence, quartz and feldspar are darker, clay and carbonate cement are brighter, coaly organic particles are black, between grains are orange stains indicating the presence of bituminous matter

XRD: Clay + Q + F + Py: 80.7 % Calcite: 0.3 % Dolomite: 0 % Dolomite Ca-Fe: 18.7 %

Fig. 5-11: ZA4, MD 1 862 m, TVDSS 1574.55 m, Caprock, Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb.

Sandstone composed (Sisa) mainly of subangular to subrounded quartz grains, less feldspar grains, and some charred organic detritus. Space between grains is almost completely filled by clay, partly with dolomite cement. In fluorescence quartz is dark green, cement is bright green, charred organic detritus is black and there is a lot of probably bituminous matter with orange color. **Porosity:** interparticle, fracture

- A) quartz grains are white, coaly organic particles are black, feldspars and clay are grey, plain light
- B) fig. C in crossed polarized light
- C) quartz grains (q), feldspars and clay are grey, plain light
- D) fig. C in XPL, tectonically affected grain of quartz with undulose extinction in centre
- E) feldspar (f), quartz (q), coaly organic particle (cp), plain light
- F) fig. E in fluorescence, quartz and feldspar are darker, clay and carbonate cement are brighter, coaly organic particles are black, between grains are orange stains indicating the presence of bituminous matter

XRD: Clay + Q + F + Py: 90.1 % Calcite: 0 % Dolomite: 9.5 % Dolomite Ca-Fe: 0.0 %

6 OPTICAL POROSITY OF RESERVOIR AND SEAL ROCKS

Optical porosity was evaluated using blue epoxy resin impregnation of the rock samples and image analysis (Fig. 6-1).

Fig. 6-1: Vranovice Fm., fracture and cavernous porosity, Optical porosity estimated by image analysis of color-coded pore space. a, b) Altered peloidal-bioclastic wackestone with fracture porosity; c, d) polymodal planar-s dolomite with cavernous porosity.

Fig. 6-2: Pore size distribution as a function of pore diameter – a) partial contribution of each pore size interval and b) cumulative porosity measured on 22 samples.

Cavernous porosity varies shows a maximum at pore diameter of 100-300 μm . Most of the matrix porosity is in the clay size range of $<10 \mu\text{m}$.

7 LITHOFACIAL 3D MODEL

Detailed well log, seismic and microscopic investigations provide basis for the lithofacial 3D model. In the following section the evolution of depositional settings is shown in a 3D model using the static model as a background. In Fig. 7-1, fourteen ZA and eight UH wells are shown with encountered lithostratigraphic intervals.

Fig. 7-1: 3D view of exploration and production wells in the Zar-3 oil and gas field and close vicinity with encountered lithostratigraphic intervals used in the lithofacial model shown in Figs. 7-2 and 7-3.

The Lower Carboniferous strata of the Myslejovice Fm. were deposited in synorogenic foreland basin settings, when the Avalon and Armorica plates converged from SW (in present sense) to the Brunovistulian plate. The front of the overriding plate supplied abundant siliciclastic material to numerous slumps and related turbidites (Krejčí et al. 1996) known in literature as “Culm” or Carboniferous Flysch facies (Fig. 7-2). The rocks underwent significant diagenesis and cementation. In the storage complex they act as an underburden seal. More than 1000-1500 m of the Carboniferous rocks were removed by later erosion during the Permian – Lower Jurassic.

In the Middle Jurassic, the Nikolčice Fm. was deposited as calcareous dolomitic sandstones on the eroded surface of the crystalline basement north of the Myslejovice Fm. in the Zar-3 area (Fig. 7-2).

Fig. 7-2: Lower Carboniferous “flysch” or turbidite facies of the Myslejovice Fm. and dolomitic sandstone shallow marine facies of the Middle Jurassic Nikolčice Fm.

Fig. 7-3: Upper Jurassic patch reef and carbonate bank facies of the Vranovice Fm. overlying the Nikolčice Fm. Well names and numbers are in Fig. 7-1.

In the Upper Jurassic shallow sea covered the Zar-3 area and the principal reservoir – dolomites of the Vranovice Fm. were deposited in patch reef and carbonate bank facies. The original limestones were dolomitized during the early diagenetic phase.

Fig. 7-4: In the Upper Jurassic, the Mikulov Fm. was deposited in basinal marl facies of the upper continental slope.

Little or no evidence has been found of an erosional contact of the Vranovice and overlying Mikulov Fm. These basinal marls with little or no dolomitization were deposited in the upper continental slope facies. In Zar-3, they represent a seal in the trap.

Fig. 7-5: In the Eocene, the Nesvačilka Fm., Žarošice Mb., was deposited in submarine canyon facies with steep flanks and slumps.

The Žarošice Mb. acts as second caprock in the Zar-3 storage complex.

8 CONCLUSIONS

Lithofacial layer model provides interpretation of the evolution of depositional environment patterns in the Zar-3 field. The model is based on well logs, seismic data interpretations and core samples analysis. It is aimed as additional information for building the 3D static geometric model (WP2), dynamic model (WP3) and risk assessment (WP6).

Well profiles are presented graphically with lithology, stratigraphy, core samples, perforations and selected well log curves. These charts are used for estimations, what depth interval is covered by the detailed lithological descriptions made on core samples.

Paleogeographic maps are prepared based on well profiles and seismic data. They show the probable preserved areal extent of the lithostratigraphic units with characteristic facial type. In many cases it was necessary to make interpolations among the well data and extrapolation to places with no well data.

Microscopic analysis of rock petrography and documentation serves as a basis for identification of more detailed facial types of dolomites and limestones and related diagenesis. Image analysis was used to evaluate optical porosity of 10 **reservoir rock** samples. The **pore size distribution** shows a maximum at 100-300 μm related to fracture and cavernous porosity type. The majority of matrix reservoir pores range, however, from 1-10 μm .

Caprocks of Paleogene and Carboniferous age show cumulative porosity of $<0.1\%$ what confirms the relative seal efficiency.

Further geochemical investigations should provide evidence on potential porosity evolution in Myslejovice formation caprocks driven by feldspar dissolution.

Lithofacial 3D model is presented based on the static 3D model with respect to the well logs, geology, petrography and microscopic analysis. It is provided for further 3D modeling and risk analysis.

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